

New Reactions of 2'-Aminovinyl- and 3-(Tetrahydropyrid-4-yl)indoles with Dienophiles

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Some new reactions of 2'-aminovinyl- and 3-(tetrahydropyrid-4-yl)indoles with dienophiles are described. The product pattern consists of Diels-Alder adducts of the carbazole series, an ene adduct and (in the case of a reaction with high nucleophilic *N*-phenyltriazoline-3,5-dione) an annelated hexahydrotriazocine derivative.

1'- or 2'-Aminosubstituted-3-vinylindoles (**I,II**) and 3-(tetrahydropyrid-4-yl)indoles (**III**) are interesting π -electron-rich compounds as building blocks for alkaloids¹⁻⁵ and especially in the case of **III** as pharmacologically interesting lead substances with antidepressant activity f.e. as 5-hydroxytryptamine receptor agonists and also as antagonists^{6,7}. In the context of the application of these diene systems for [*b*]-annellation of the indole skeleton⁸, we have reported first results of the 4π reactivity of some of these functionalised compounds towards several dienophiles so far¹⁻³. In the present paper, we present in continuation of our studies of pericyclic reactions with indole derivatives⁷ some further results on reactions of vinylindoles (**2a,2b,5a,5b**) and of 3-(tetrahydropyrid-4-yl)indoles (**9a,9b**) with *N*-phenylmaleimide and in one case with highly dienophilic 4-phenyl-4*H*-1,2,4-triazoline-3,5-dione (PTAD).

Results and Discussion

Synthetic aspects : According to the procedure described in earlier³, the respective *N*-methylindole-carbinols **1a,1b** and **5a,5b** as precursors to vinylindoles were synthesised as a mixture of stereoisomers starting from the respective indole-carbaldehydes via an *Horner-Wittig* strategy. Treatment of carbinols **1a,1b** or **5a,5b** with potassium hydride gave rise to vinylindoles **2a,2b** or **6a,6b** respectively. However, the highly electron-rich vinylindoles **2** and **6** polymerised when

purified. They were therefore used as crude products and subsequently submitted to Diels-Alder reactions with *N*-phenylmaleimide as dienophile. In the case of starting compound **1a,1b**, the primarily formed Diels-Alder products **3a,3b** were also unstable. Dehydrogenation of **3a,3b** with 2,3-dichloro-5,6-dicyano-1,4-benzoquinone (DDQ) gave rise to more stable coplanar pyrrolo[*a*]carbazoles **4a,4b**. In the case of reaction with **5a,5b** the crude vinylindoles **6a,6b** reacted with *N*-phenylmaleimide to characterisable Diels-Alder adducts **7a,7b**. ¹H nmr spectroscopic analysis revealed that the (*E*)-stereoisomer of **6a,6b** has

reacted throughout. Dehydrogenation of **7a,7b** with DDQ exclusively yielded elimination product **8** (Chart 1).

Chart 1

The 3-(tetrahydropyrid-4-yl)indoles **9a,9b** are readily available by proton acid-catalysed condensation of the respective indoles with *N*-methylpiperid-4-one according to a related procedure already described⁹ in very good to sufficient yield. In the case of the reaction with the indole parent compound, the yield is diminished by the unavoidable production of the C_s symmetric spiro-compound **10** (30% yield) (Chart 2). However, the Diels-Alder reactivity of **9a,9b** is in general low. But **9a** reacts with the dienophile *N*-phenylmaleimide (NPMI) in refluxing DMF according to a dehydrogenative [4+2] cycloaddition to pyrrolopyrido-anellated carbazole **11** in 14% yield. The electronically more reactive indole derivative **9b** reacts in refluxing toluene with *N*-phenylmaleimide to *endo*-cycloadduct **12** and in poor yield additionally to ene adduct **13**.

Interestingly, **9b** was transformed with 4-phenyl-4*H*-1,2,4-triazolin-3,5-dione (PTAD) to a primarily

Chart 2

unexpected anellated hexahydrotriazocine derivative **14**. As mechanism we suggest that in the first step regioselective electrophilic addition of PTAD onto the electron-rich double bond in the tetrahydropyridine ring gives rise to betaine **I** (Scheme 1). Heterolytic ring cleavage reaction of the piperidine system should give rise to betaine intermediate **II** with an iminium moiety, which cyclises regiocontrolled to the anellated eight-membered product **14** respectively. However, the cyclisation step from **II** to **14** is full compatible according to the *Baldwin* rules (8-*endo*-trig process)¹⁰.

Structural investigations of products : The constitution and in the case of compounds **7** and **12** the relative configuration were unambiguously established by high resolution (200 and 400 MHz) ¹H nmr spectroscopy, whereas ¹H ¹H noe measurements shed light into the structural interrelationships of the systems. As for example for compound **12** typical noe from angular methyl group 7b-β to the three β-positioned bridge protons H7a,H4b,H4a is mostly indicative

Scheme 1

of *endo*-configuration. The unusual constitution of the triazacyclooctene derivative **14** was supported by *ei*-, *fd*- mass fragmentation (1 : 1 adduct) and more sophisticatedly by ^{13}C nmr spin echo and SFORD (single frequency off resonance decoupling) experiments. In spite of rapid ring inversion, the 400 MHz ^1H nmr spectrum at -90° was analysed. Under these conditions, the C10- CH_2 group centered at 4.9 ppm reflects the typical AB spin system with a geminal coupling constant of 14 Hz. The analogous CH_2 carbon resonance in the ^{13}C nmr spectrum is registered at 65.8 ppm in CDCl_3 and supports the 'aminal moiety' N11-C10-N9. MAXIMIN2 force field calculations¹¹ predict unrestricted rotation about the C3'-C6-sigma bond (Fig. 1). The highest energy barrier according to SEARCH conformational analysis¹¹ is only 14.6 kcal mol⁻¹ (E_{steric}). These theoretical con-

Fig. 1 MAXIMIN2 force field calculated low energy conformation of **14**¹¹.

siderations support the experimental results of ^1H , ^1H noe measurements at 400 MHz (room temperature), which demonstrated typical noe from H5 to indole-2'-methyl group and to indole H4', respectively.

Experimental

^1H nmr spectra were recorded at 200 and 400 MHz with Bruker AC 200 and AMX 400 spectrometers. ^{13}C nmr spectra were measured at 50.3 MHz with Bruker AC 200 instrument. *J*-modulated spin echo spectra were listed for C_p = primary, C_s = secondary, C_t = tertiary, and C_q = quarternary carbon atoms. The *ei* (70 eV) and *fd* mass spectra were recorded on a Varian MAT 7 spectrometer. Elemental analysis was performed using a Carlo Erba Strumentazione 1106 apparatus. Melting points were measured with an Electrothermal 9200 instrument. Flash chromatography was performed on Merck 60 silica gel (particle size : 0.040–0.063 mm). Petroleum ether used had the boiling range 40–60°. All reactions were performed under argon atmosphere.

Diphenyl-[2-hydroxy-2-(1-methylindol-3-yl)-1-(pyrrolidin-1-yl)ethyl]phosphine oxide (1a) : To diphenyl-[(pyrrolidin-1-yl)methyl]phosphine oxide (1.43 g, 5 mmol) dissolved in tetrahydrofuran (30 ml) was added *t*-butyllithium (5 ml, 1.7 m *n*-pentane solution) at -78° slowly until the mixture turned red coloured and then 1-methylindole-3-carbaldehyde (0.875 g, 5.5 mmol in 20 ml tetrahydrofuran) was added. After stirring for 1 h the mixture was quenched with aqueous ammonium chloride (50 ml; 20%). The crude product obtained by extraction of the mixture with dichloromethane, was purified by crystallisation from dichloromethane/diethyl ether, (1.3 g, 60%), m.p. 154° (Found : C, 72.78; H, 6.54; N, 6.27. $\text{C}_{27}\text{H}_{29}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2\text{P}$ (444.51) calcd. for : C, 72.96; H, 6.58; N 6.30%); ^1H nmr (200 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 1.48 (4H, m, pyrrolidine-3- CH_2 , -4- CH_2), 3.00 (4H, m, pyrrolidine-2- CH_2 , -5- CH_2), 3.35 (3H, s, indole-N-Me), 4.33 (2H, m), 5.49 (1H, dd, $^3J_{(\text{C1-H}, \text{C2-H})}$ 8.7 Hz, 2J 3.85 Hz,

C1-H), 6.80 (1H, s, indole-C2-H), 6.86–7.78 (14H, m, ArH); EIMS m/z (%) 426 (0.7), 201 (18), 144 (4), 84 (100).

Diphenyl-[2-hydroxy-2-(1-methyl-indol-3-yl)-1-(4-methylpiperazin-1-yl)ethyl]phosphine oxide (1b) : The procedure was the same as preparation of **1a** except that diphenyl-[(4-methyl-piperazin-1-yl)ethyl]phosphine oxide was used : (yield 1.23 g, 53%), m.p. 145° (Found : C, 72.38; H, 6.92; N, 8.96. $C_{28}H_{32}N_3O_2P$ (463.55) calcd. for : C, 72.55; H, 6.96; N 9.06%); 1H nmr (200 MHz, $CDCl_3$) δ 2.08 (4H, m, piperazine-3- CH_2 , -5- CH_2), 2.15 (3H, s, piperazine-N-Me), 2.92 (4H, m, piperazine-2- CH_2 , -6- CH_2), 3.37 (3H, m, indole-N-Me), 3.47 (1H, m), 4.03 (1H, dd, $^3J_{(C1-H C2-H)}$ 8.01 Hz, J 5.11 Hz, C2-H), 5.63 (1H, dd, $^3J_{(C1-H C2-H)}$ 7.99 Hz, J 3.67 Hz, C1-H), 6.84 (1H, s, indole-C2-H), 6.88–7.84 (14H, m, ArH); EIMS m/z (%) 314 (9), 201 (22), 144 (11), 113 (100).

(E/Z)-1-Methyl-3-[2-[pyrrolidin-1-yl]ethenyl]indole (2a) : To carbinol **1a** (0.9 g, 2 mmol) dissolved in dry tetrahydrofuran was added potassium hydride (241 mg, 6 mmol) and after stirring at room temperature n-hexane (200 ml) and water (50 ml) were added. The organic layer was separated and the aqueous phase was extracted several times with dichloromethane. The combined organic phases was dried over $MgSO_4$ and concentrated. The resulting crude vinylindole was immediately submitted to a Diels-Alder reaction, because of its very unstable (polymerisation) nature.

(E/Z)-1-Methyl-3-[2-(4-methylpiperazin-1-yl) ethenyl]indole (2b) : It was prepared according to procedure of compound **2a**.

10-Methyl-2-phenyl-4-(pyrrolidin-1-yl)-1,2,3,10-tetrahydropyrrolo[3,4-a]carbazol-1,3-dione (4a) :

To 3-vinylindole (**2a**) was dissolved in dichloromethane (30 ml), *N*-phenylmaleimide (0.35 g, 2 mmol) was added. After a reaction time of 30 min at room temperature the product was oxidised by 2,3-dichloro-5,6-dicyano-1,4-ben-

zoquinone (0.9 g, 4 mmol) by refluxing the mixture for 1 h. Then, the mixture was poured onto ice and extracted with a saturated solution of $NaHCO_3$. The organic layer was dried over $MgSO_4$ and evaporated. The residue was purified by flash chromatography (ethyl acetate/2-propanol, 9 : 1), (95 mg, 12%), m.p. 165° (Found : C, 75.7; H, 5.29; N, 10.51. $C_{25}H_{21}N_3O_2$ (395.46) calcd. for : C, 75.93; H, 5.35; N, 10.63%); 1H nmr (200 MHz, $DMSO-d_6$) δ 1.43 (4H, m, pyrrolidine-3- CH_2 , -4- CH_2), 2.87 (4H, m, pyrrolidine-2- CH_2 , -5- CH_2), 3.49 (3H, s, indole-N-Me), 6.75–6.93 (8H, m, ArH), 7.55 (1H, s, C5-H), 7.61 (1H, d, J 7.58 Hz); EIMS m/z (%) 395 (4), 326 (100), 173 (23).

10-Methyl-4-(4-methylpiperazin-1-yl)-2-phenyl-1,2,3,10-tetrahydropyrrolo[3,4-a]carbazol-1,3-dione (4b) : It was prepared according to the synthetic procedure of **4a**, (68 mg, 9%), m.p. 178° (Found : C, 73.41; H, 5.59; N, 13.14. $C_{26}H_{24}N_4O_2$ (424.50) calcd for : C, 73.57; H, 5.70; N, 13.20%); 1H nmr (200 MHz, $DMSO-d_6$) δ 1.52 (3H, s, piperazine-N-Me), 1.60–1.85 (8H, m, piperazine-H), 3.56 (3H, s, indole-N-Me), 6.67–6.84 (8H, m, ArH), 7.51 (1H, s, C5-H), 7.58 (1H, d, J 7.74 Hz, ArH); EIMS m/z (%) 424 (53), 355 (100), 327 (3).

Diphenyl-[2-hydroxy-2-(1-methylindol-2-yl)-1-(pyrrolidin-1-yl)ethyl]phosphine oxide (5a) : It was prepared according to the synthetic procedure of **1a** from 1-methylindole-2-carbaldehyde, yield 1.2 g, (53%); m.p. 165° (Found : C, 72.79; H, 6.51; N, 6.18. $C_{27}H_{29}N_2O_2P$ (444.51) calcd. for : C, 72.96; H, 6.58; N 6.30%); 1H nmr (200 MHz, $CDCl_3$) δ 1.52 (4H, m, pyrrolidin-3- CH_2 , -4- CH_2), 3.05 (4H, m, pyrrolidine-2- CH_2 , -4- CH_2), 3.61 (3H, s, indole-N-Me), 4.17 (1H, dd, $^3J_{(C1-H C2-H)}$ 7.69 Hz, J 3.07 Hz, C2-H), 5.36 (2H, m), 6.40 (1H, s, indole-C3-H), 6.90–7.07 (6H, m, ArH), 7.31–7.52 (6H, m, ArH), 7.79–7.89 (2H, m, ArH); EIMS m/z (%) 285 (0.1), 201 (21), 144 (3), 84 (100) *

Diphenyl-[2-hydroxy-2-(1-methylindol-2-yl)-1-(4-methylpiperazin-1-yl)ethyl]phosphine oxide (5b)

It was synthesised according to the procedure for the synthesis of compound **1b** except that 1-methylindole-2-carbaldehyde was used : yield (1.6 g, 68%) (Found : C, 72.50; H, 6.89; N, 9.00. m.p. 172°. $C_{28}H_{32}N_3O_2$ (463.55) calcd. for : C, 72.55; H, 6.96; N, 9.06%); 1H nmr (200 MHz, $CDCl_3$) δ 2.02 (3H, s, piperazine-N-Me), 2.14 (4H, m, piperazine-3- CH_2 , -5- CH_2), 3.07 (4H, m, piperazine-2- CH_2 , -6- CH_2), 3.63 (3H, s, indole-N-Me), 3.83 (2H, m), 5.51 (1H, dd, $^3J_{(Cl-H,C2-H)}$ 8.54 Hz, J 3.82 Hz, C1-H), 6.40 (1H, s, indole-C3-H), 6.90–7.06 (6H, m, ArH), 7.29–7.50 (6H, m, ArH), 7.75–7.86 (2H, m, ArH); EIMS m/z (%) 314 (1), 201 (6), 113 (30), 70 (100).

(*E/Z*)-1-Methyl-2-[2-(pyrrolidin-1-yl)ethenyl]indole (**6a**) and (*E/Z*)-1-methyl-2-[2-(4-methylpiperazin-1-yl)ethenyl]indole (**6b**) were synthesised according to the procedure for the preparation of **2a**. The crude products were immediately submitted to Diels-Alder reactions.

6-Methyl-4 α -(pyrrolidin-1-yl)-2-phenyl-1,2,3,3a β ,4 β ,5,6,10c β -octahydroindolo[3,4-*c*]carbazol-1,3-dione (**7a**) : To the crude product **6a** dissolved in dry dichloromethane (30 ml), *N*-phenylmaleimide (0.35 g, 2 mmol) was added. After stirring at room temperature for 12 h, the mixture was directly purified by flash chromatography (ethyl acetate), (120 mg 14%), m.p. 183° (Found : C, 74.99; H, 6.39; N, 10.62. $C_{25}H_{25}N_3O$ (399.49) calcd. for : C, 75.16; H, 6.31; N, 10.52%); 1H nmr (400 MHz, CCl_2D_2) δ 1.62 (4H, m, pyrrolidine-3- CH_2 , -4- CH_2), 1.82 (4H, m, pyrrolidine-2- CH_2 , -5- CH_2), 2.92 (1H, m, 5-H), 3.08 (1H, dd, J 16.1 Hz, J 4.5 Hz, C5-H), 3.14 (1H, m, C4), 3.66 (3H, s, indole-N-Me), 3.78 (1H, dd, J 4.66 Hz, J 7.69 Hz, C3 α -H), 4.45 (1H, d, J 7.76 Hz, C10c-H), 7.09–7.42 (8H, m, ArH), 7.89 (1H, d, J 7.82 Hz); EIMS m/z (%) 399 (M^{+} , 15), 225 (9), 173 (7), 149 (100).

6-Methyl-4 α -(4-methylpiperazin-1-yl)-2-phenyl-1,2,3,3a β ,4 β ,5,6,10c β -octahydroindolo[3,4-*c*]carbazol-1,3-dione (**7b**) : It was synthesised according

to the procedure described for compound **7a** : (yield 140 mg, 7%), m.p. 162° (Found : C, 72.75; H, 6.68; N, 13.20. $C_{26}H_{28}N_4O_2$ (428.53) calcd. for : C, 72.87; H, 6.59; N, 13.07%); 1H nmr (200 MHz, $CDCl_3$) δ 2.01 (3H, s, piperazine-N-Me), 2.5–2.85 (6H, m, aliphatic-H), 2.96 (4H, m, aliphatic-H), 3.45 (1H, dd, J 5.9 Hz, J 10.7 Hz), 3.67 (3H, s, indole-N-Me), 3.72 (1H, m), 4.44 (1H, d, J 7.9 Hz, C10c-H), 6.89–7.43 (8H, m, ArH), 7.95 (1H, d, J 7.31 Hz); EIMS m/z 428.9 (M^{+} , 2.4), 328 (100), 254 (0.6).

6-Methyl-2-phenyl-1,2,3,6-tetrahydropyrrolo[3,4-*c*]carbazol-1,3-dione (**8**) : To compound **7a** or **7b** dissolved in THF (10 ml), was added DDQ (0.22 g, 1 mmol) and the whole mixture was refluxed for 1 h. The mixture was then poured onto ice and extracted with saturated aqueous solution of $NaHCO_3$. The organic layer was separated and dried over $MgSO_4$. The resulting residue was purified by flash chromatography (ethyl acetate) : yield from **7a**, 69 mg (85%); yield from **7b**, 67 mg (88%) (Found : C, 77.37; H, 4.51; N, 8.66. $C_{21}H_{14}N_2O_3$ (326.35) calcd. for : C, 77.29, H, 4.32, N, 8.58%); 1H nmr (200 MHz, $CDCl_3$) δ 3.88 (3H, s, indole-N-Me), 7.33–7.63 (9H, m, ArH), 7.96 (1H, d, J 8.3 Hz, C5-H), 9.01 (1H, d, J 8.3 Hz, C4-H); EIMS m/z (%) 326 (M^{+} , 100), 282 (36), 179 (24).

3-(1-Methyl-1,2,3,6-tetrahydropyrid-4-yl)indole (**9a**) and 1,2-dimethyl-3-(1-methyl-1,2,3,6-tetrahydropyrid-4-yl)indole (**9b**) : These were synthesised by the reported method⁹. Besides the formation of **9a**, 4,4-di(3-indolyl)-1-methylpiperidine (**10**) was produced : **9a** (45%) m.p. 215° (ethanol), 210–220°⁹; **9b** : from 1,2-dimethylindole (3 g, 0.021 mol), *N*-methylpiperid-4-one (4.75 g, 0.042 mol), acetic acid (60 ml) and 2 *N* phosphoric acid (15 ml), reaction time 2 h at 80°. The crude product was crystallised from diethyl ether, (4.81 g, 96%), m.p. 79° (Found : C, 79.95; H, 8.55; N, 11.42. $C_{16}H_{20}N_2$ (240.35) calcd. for : C, 79.96; H, 8.38; N, 11.65%); 1H nmr (400 MHz, $DMSO-d_6$) δ 2.28

(3H, s, Me), 2.35 (3H, s, piperidenyl-NMe), 2.45 (2H, m_c, piperidenyl-CH₂), 2.57 (2H, m_c, piperidenyl-CH₂), 3.02 (2H, m_c, piperidenyl-CH₂), 3.63 (3H, s, indole-NMe), 5.55 (1H, m_c, vinyl-H), 6.93–7.43 (4H, m, ArH); ¹³C nmr (CDCl₃) δ 11.02 (indole-C2-Me), 29.41 (NMe), 31.03 (C_s), 45.96 (indole-NMe), 52.59 (C_s), 55.06 (C_s), 108.53 (C_l), 114.64 (C_q), 119.01 (C_l), 120.60 (2 × C_l), 123.78 (C_l), 126.64 (C_q), 130.41 (C_q), 132.69 (C_q), 136.41 (C_q); EIMS *m/z* (%) 240 (*M*⁺) (100), 225 (38), 182 (43).

4,4-Di-(3-indolyl)-1-methylpiperidine (10) : Besides product **9a** (3.9 g, 30%) compound **10** was formed which was crystallised from methanol, m.p. 295–300^o (Found : C, 80.15; H, 7.10; N, 12.67. C₂₂H₂₃N₃ (329.15) calcd. for : C, 80.20; H, 7.03; N, 12.75%); ¹H nmr (200 MHz, DMSO-d₆) δ 2.20 (3H, s), 2.3–2.8 (8H, m), 6.5–7.5 (10H, m), 10.8 (2H, s, NH); EIMS *m/z* (%) 329 (*M*⁺) (100).

3-Methyl-1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8-octahydro-6-phenylpyrido[3,4-c]pyrrolo[3,4-a]carbazol-5,7-dione (11) : A mixture of **9a** (1 g, 4.72 mmol), *N*-phenylmaleimide (900 mg, 5.2 mmol) and hydroquinone (70 mg) was dissolved in DMF (100 ml) and refluxed for 24 h. After cooling, the mixture was concentrated under reduced pressure and the residue was dissolved in a few ml of ethyl acetate and purified by flash chromatography (ethyl acetate), (250 mg, 14%), m.p. 262^o (ethanol) (Found : C, 75.48; H, 5.23; N, 10.97. C₂₄H₁₉N₃O₂ (381.44) calcd. for : C, 75.57; H, 5.02; N, 11.02%); ¹H nmr (400 MHz, DMSO-d₆) δ 2.45 (3H, s, NMe), 2.84 (2H, m_c, piperidenyl-CH₂), 3.49 (2H, m_c, piperidenyl-CH₂), 4.01 (2H, s, piperidenyl-CH₂), 7.26–8.19 (9H, m, ArH), 12.11 (1H, s, NH); EIMS *m/z* (%) 381 (*M*⁺) (62), 57 (100)

1,2,3,4,4aβ,4bβ,5,6,7aβ,7bβ,8-Dodecahydro-3,7bα,β-trimethyl-6-phenyl-pyrido[3,4-c]pyrrolo[3,4-a]carbazol-5,7-dione (and enantiomer) (12) and 1-phenyl-3-[4-(1,2-dimethylindol-3-yl)-1-methyl-1,2,3,6-tetrahydropyrid-4-yl]pyrrolidin-2,5-dione (13) : A mixture of **9b** (750 mg, 3.12 mmol), *N*-phenyl-

maleimide (510 mg, 3.2 mmol) and hydroquinone (50 mg) was refluxed in toluene (50 ml) for 7 h. The mixture was then concentrated under reduced pressure and the residue purified by flash chromatography (ethyl acetate). Products **12** and **13** were thus separated : **12** (500 mg, 39%), m.p. 210^o (Found : C, 75.48; H, 6.44; N, 10.22. C₂₆H₂₇N₃O₂ (413.52) calcd. for : C, 75.52; H, 6.58; N, 10.11%); ¹H nmr (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 1.11 (3H, d, C7b-Me), 1.23 (1H, ³J, 2.4 Hz, piperidylidene-H), 1.98 (1H, m_c, piperidylidene-H), 2.13 (1H, m_c, piperidylidene-H), 2.41 (3H, s, N3-Me), 2.71–2.80 (1H, m, piperidylidene-H), 2.81 (dd, ³J, 8.7 Hz, 10.2 Hz, C4b-H), 3.01–3.12 (2H, m, piperidylidene-H), 3.05 (3H, s, N8-Me), 3.48 (1H, d, ³J 10.3 Hz, C7a-H), 3.69 (1H, m, C4a-H), 6.53 (1H, d, ³J 7.3 Hz, C9-H), 6.70 (1H, t, 7.1 Hz, C11-H), 7.16 (t, ³J, 7.3 Hz, C10-H), 7.28 (2H, d, ³J 7.2 Hz, phenyl-H), 7.37–7.43 (2H, m, C12- and phenyl-H), 7.48 (2H, t, ³J 7.5 Hz, phenyl-H); EIMS *m/z* (%) 413 (*M*⁺) (56), 44 (100); **13** (120 mg, 9%), m.p. 162^o (diethyl ether) (Found : C, 75.09; H, 6.49; N, 10.09. calcd. for : C, 75.52; H, 6.58; N, 10.16%); ¹H nmr (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 2.38 (3H, s, indole-C2-Me), 2.44 (1H, m_c, aliphatic-H), 2.52 (3H, s, NMe), 2.68 (6H, m, aliphatic-H), 3.57 (1H, m_c, aliphatic-H), 3.63 (3H, s, indole-NMe), 3.76 (1H, m_c, aliphatic-H), 5.30 (1H, m_c, vinyl-H), 7.02–7.46 (9H, m, ArH); EIMS *m/z* (%) 413 (*M*⁺) (3), 239 (100); fd-MS 413 (*M*⁺) (100).

1,2,3,4,5,6-Hexahydro-6-(1,2-dimethylindol-3-yl)-9-methyl-2-phenyl[1,2,4]triazolo[1,2-a]-[1,2,4]triazocine (14) : Compound **9b** (275 mg, 1.14 mmol) was dissolved in dichloromethane (30 ml) and cooled to –78^o. To this mixture PTAD (240 mg, 1.37 mmol) dissolved in dichloromethane (20 ml) was added slowly under stirring. After 1 h the mixture was concentrated under reduced pressure and the residue obtained was purified by flash chromatography (ethyl acetate), (95 mg, 20%), m.p. 166^o (ethyl acetate) (Found : C, 69.32; H, 6.18; N, 17.02. C₂₄H₂₅N₅O₂ (415.20)

calcd. for : C, 69.36; H, 6.07; N, 16.86%); ^1H nmr (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 2.49 (3H, s, indol-C3-Me), 2.57 (3H, s, NMe), 2.84 (2H, m, azocine-C7- CH_2), 3.04 (2H, m, azocine-C8- CH_2), 3.70 (3H, s, indole-N-Me), 4.87 (s, aminal-azocine- CH_2), 6.34 (1H, s, vinyl-C5-H), 7.12 (dd, 3J 7.6 Hz, 7.7 Hz, indole-C5- or C6-H), 7.20 (dd, 3J 7.3 Hz, 7.6 Hz, indole-C6- or C5-H), 7.29 (2H, d, 3J 7.2 Hz, indol-C7-H), 7.35 (1H, pt, 3J 7.2 Hz, 7.3 Hz, phenyl-C4-H), 7.47 (2H, pt, 7.8 Hz, 7.7 Hz, phenyl-C3- and C5-H), 7.56 (1H, d, 7.9 Hz, indole-C4-H), 7.56 (pt, 3J 7.9 Hz, phenyl-C2- and C6-H); ^{13}C nmr (50.3 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 1.48 (indole-C2-Me), 28.15 (C_s), 29.72 (N-Me), 37.29 (indole-N-Me), 55.31 (C_s), 65.76 (C_s , aminal C10), 109.01 (C_t), 111.75 (C_q), 117.48 (vinyl-C5), 118.69 (C_t), 119.93 (C_t), 121.42 (C_t), 125.47 ($2 \times \text{C}_t$), 126.78 (C_q), 127.96 (C_t), 129.04 ($2 \times \text{C}_t$), 131.66 (C_q), 134.74 (C_q), 136.71 (C_q), 138.28 (C_q), 149.56 (C=O), 151.97 (C=O); EIMS m/z (%) 415 ($M^{+\bullet}$) (24), 237 (100); fd-MS 415 ($M^{+\bullet}$) (100).

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